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Thermal Radiation and Thermo-Diffusional influence of MHD Unsteady Heat Mass Transfer Flow over an exponentially vertical Plates

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of thermo-diffusion and thermal radiative MHD flow over an exponentially vertical plate. The governing non-linear partial differential equations, along with their initial and boundary conditions were converted into a dimensionless form using appropriate dimensional variables. The equations were later solved using a numerical method called finite element method. The results, presented through graphs and tables. From the results outcome it was reveal that fluid velocity increases with higher values of the Brinkman number (B_r), perturbation parameter (ϵ), solutal Grashof number (G_c), thermal grashof number (G_r) and radiation parameter (R). In contrast, an increase in the Hall current parameter (m) and the magnetic field parameter (M) leads to a reduction in velocity. The temperature profile is enhanced as the radiation parameter (R) increases but diminishes with higher values of the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β), Prandtl number (P_r) and magnetic parameter (M). In terms of concentration, an increase in the chemical reaction rate reduces concentration, while higher Soret number (S_r) leads to its increase. Additionally, skin friction (τ), Nusselt number (N_u) and Sherwood number (S_h) rise significantly with higher radiation parameter (R) and solutal grashof number (G_c) but they experience a slight reduction with increasing Jeffrey fluid parameter (β). Overall, the findings align well with results from previous studies.

Keywords: Thermal-Radiative, Hall current, Thermo-diffusion, coquette Flow

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermo-diffusion, also known as the Soret effect, plays a significant role in double-diffusive convection, particularly in light and medium molecular weight fluids. The Soret effect refers to mass flux in the concentration equation induced by temperature gradients. Research on both Soret and Dufour effects has gained the attention of many scholars. For instance, Taid & Ahmed(2022) studied MHD viscous dissipative flow with ohmic heating in an inclined porous plate under the influence of a heat source and chemical reaction. Similarly, Isah & Abdullah (2021) reported that the velocity profile increases with the Dufour number in their work on MHD Couette flow through free convective vertical channels, considering buoyancy and thermal diffusion .In their analysis of Maxwell nanofluids subjected to nonlinear thermal radiation over a stretching porous plate, Williams & Yabo (2024) found that both velocity and temperature profiles increase as the Soret number rises. Isah & Abdullah (2020) also

observed that velocity grows with an increase in the Soret number during their study on MHD Couette flow with buoyancy effects. Additionally, Borah et al. (2023) examined MHD micropolar fluids over vertical Riga plates and confirmed that higher Soret numbers lead to improved velocity profiles. Further research by Kayalvizhi et al. (2024) explored MHD flow past a stretching permeable sheet in the presence of chemical reactions and viscous dissipation, considering both Soret and Dufour effects. Raghunath (2023) investigated water-based nanofluids in MHD heat and mass transfer over a stretching sheet under transverse magnetic fields with Soret and thermal radiation influences. Raghunath (2023) studied MHD free convective flow over vertical permeable sheets under heat generation and radiation. The role of Soret effects in Casson fluid was analyzed by Abbas et al. (2024) using a Caputo fractional derivative approach in an MHD flow over an accelerated plate. Moreover, Ramesh et al. (2023) reported that the Dufour effect enhances the concentration profile in their analysis of MHD Casson fluid flow in porous channels under Soret. In another relevant study Isah et al. (2025) examined MHD free convection in coaxial cylinders, considering entropy generation under non-thermal radiation and isoflux conditions.

The hall-current is defined as an induced current normal to the magnetic field; it is a key aspect of MHD studies due to its applications in devices like Hall accelerators, refrigerator coils, and electric transformers. Raju & Rao (2021) analyzed heat transfer in two-ionized MHD fluid flow and found that the primary velocity increases with the Hall current parameter. Saleh et al. (2022) investigated MHD Jeffery fluid flow with heat absorption over a vertical porous plate, while Mogirango & Chepkwony (2023) reported improvements in the temperature profile due to increased inclination in MHD heat and mass transfer over inclined porous plates. Furthermore, Rao et al. (2024) examined two-ionized fluid MHD flow in conducting channels and found that increasing the Hall current parameter enhances velocity. Demis et al. (2024) analyzed MHD Casson nanofluids over vertical stretching sheets, considering Hall currents and nonlinear thermal radiation. Liu et al. (2024) carried out a numerical simulation of MHD heat transfer models to estimate parameters in space-dependent flows. Rana et al. (2023) studied shear-thinning fluids in radiative absorption mediums with Hall current effects. Abdullahi et al. (2022) also found that velocity profiles intensify with increasing buoyancy parameters in MHD unsteady heat and mass transfer under Hall current influence. Similarly, Rauf et al. (2022; Rehman et al. (2022; Ullah et al. (2022) confirmed that Hall current has a positive effect on velocity in MHD heat and mass transfer flows.

The current study extends the work of Abdullahi et al. (2024) who analyzed unsteady MHD heat and mass transfer involving Jeffery fluids and chemical reactions under ramped temperatures. The objective here is to expand that model by incorporating thermo-diffusion phenomena under thermal radiation over an exponentially vertical plates. The findings of this research are expected to have practical implications across various engineering and scientific fields, such as hall-effect accelerators, refrigeration coils, electric transformers, liquid crystals, biological fluid flow (e.g., blood flow in the brain), colloidal suspensions, and more.

2. Formulation of the Problem

This study investigates the effects of thermo-diffusion and thermal radiative MHD flow over an exponentially vertical plate. The physical configuration of the flow is illustrated below:

Figure 1: Geometry of Flow

In this setup, the x-axis is oriented along the vertical upward direction of the plate, while the y-axis is normal (perpendicular) to the plate. The surface temperature of the plate undergoes small-amplitude oscillations around a non-uniform mean temperature. The fluid is assumed to have constant physical properties, except for density variations with temperature and concentration, which are only accounted for in the body force terms via the Boussinesq approximation. The temperature of the fluid also oscillates slightly around a non-uniform state. The flow is considered to be: unsteady and laminar, along a sufficiently long plate and therefore physical quantities depend only on time (t) and the normal coordinate (y). Additionally, a uniform magnetic field is applied perpendicular to the plate. Due to the influence of the inclined magnetic field, Hall current, thermal radiation, and chemical reactions, the governing flow is described by a system of non-linear partial differential equations:

$$\frac{\partial u^*}{\partial t^*} = \left(\frac{1}{1+\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u^*}{\partial y^{*2}} + g\beta^*(C^* - C_\infty^*) + g\beta^*(T^* - T_\infty^*) - \left(\frac{m}{1+m^2} M \sin^2 \epsilon\right) \frac{\sigma}{\rho} \beta_0^2 u^* \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial T^*}{\partial t^*} = \frac{k}{\rho c_p} \frac{\partial^2 T^*}{\partial y^{*2}} + Ec \left[\frac{du^*}{dy^*}\right]^2 - (T^* - T_\infty^*) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial C^*}{\partial t^*} = D \frac{\partial^2 C^*}{\partial y^{*2}} + \frac{(T^* - T_0^*)}{(C_w^* - C_\infty^*)} \frac{\partial T^*}{\partial t^*} - K_r^*(C^* - C_\infty^*) \quad (3)$$

The following are initial and boundary condition in their non-dimensional form:

$$t^* \leq 0: u^* = 0, T^* = T_0, \varphi^* = C_0 \text{ for all } 0 \leq y^* \leq L$$

$$t^* > 0 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} u^* = \frac{u}{U_0} e^{at}, T^* = T_w^*, \text{ at } y^* = 0 \\ u^* = 0, T^* = T_\infty^*, \text{ at } y^* = \infty \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

We have the following dimensional quantities to be used in changing the dimensional governing partial differential equations into their dimensionless form:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} U_0 = (vg\beta\Delta T)^{\frac{1}{3}}, L = \left(\frac{g\beta\Delta T}{v^2}\right)^{-\frac{1}{3}}, T_R = \left(\frac{g\beta\Delta T}{v^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right)^{-\frac{2}{3}} \\ \Delta T = T_w^* - T_\infty^*, t = \frac{t^*}{T_R}, y = \frac{y^*}{L} \\ u = \frac{u^*}{U_0}, K = \frac{K^*}{vT_R}, \theta = \frac{T^* - T_\infty^*}{T_w^* - T_\infty^*}, \varphi = \frac{C^* - C_\infty^*}{C_w^* - C_\infty^*}, S_r = \frac{S_t(T^* - T_0^*)}{\alpha(C_w^* - C_\infty^*)} \\ Pr = \frac{\mu C_p}{k}, Ec = \frac{U_0^2}{C_p \Delta T}, N = \frac{\beta^*}{\beta(T_w^* - T_\infty^*)}, M = \frac{\sigma \beta_0^2 u}{\rho u^2} \\ R = \frac{16a\sigma^* v^2 T_\infty^*}{u^2 \rho C_p}, K_r = \frac{K r_0 u}{u^2}, S_c = \frac{v}{D}, G_c = \frac{g\beta^* v (C_w^* - C_\infty^*)}{u^3} \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) was applied to change the equations (1) to (4) into dimensionless form as follows:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{1}{1+\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + Gr\theta + G_c\varphi - \left(\frac{m}{1+m^2} M \sin^2 \epsilon\right) \left(M + \frac{1}{K}\right) u \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{Pr} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} + Ec \left[\frac{du}{dy}\right]^2 + R\theta \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial t} = Sc \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial y^2} + Sr \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} - K_r \varphi \quad (8)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} t \leq 0: u = 0, \theta = 0, \varphi = 0 \text{ for all } y \\ \text{For } t \geq 0: u = e^{at}, \theta = 1, \varphi = 1 \text{ at } y = 0 \\ u = 0, \theta \rightarrow 0, \text{ at } y \rightarrow \infty \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

3. Method of the Solution

To find the numerical solution of equation (6) and (7) and (8) under the boundary conditions (9), finite element (FEM) was employed

Now application of finite element method (Galerkin's approach) on equations (6) and (7) and (8) over an element $e, y_i \leq y \leq y_j$ we have:

$$\int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T \left\{ \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{1}{1+\beta}\right) \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + Gr\varphi + G_c\varphi - \left(\frac{m}{1+m^2} M \sin^2 \epsilon\right) \left(M + \frac{1}{K}\right) u \right\} dy = 0 \quad (10)$$

Equation (8) is reduced to

$$\int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T \left\{ M_2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + P - uM_1 \right\} dy = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$M_2 = (1 + \alpha) \left(\frac{1}{1+\beta}\right) \text{ and } M_1 = \left(\frac{m}{1+m^2} M \sin^2 \epsilon\right) \left(M + \frac{1}{K}\right), P = Gr\theta + G_c\varphi$$

Applying integration by parts on (8) gives:

$$N^T \left[M_2 \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \right]_{y_i}^{y_j} - \int_{y_i}^{y_j} M_2 \frac{\partial N^T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} dy - \int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} dy - M_1 \int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T u dy + P \int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T dy = 0 = 0 \quad (12)$$

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$$M_2 \int_{y_i}^{y_j} \frac{\partial N^T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} dy + \int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} dy + M_1 \int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T u dy - P \int_{y_i}^{y_j} N^T dy = 0 = 0 \quad (13)$$

We now take $u^{(e)} = u_i N_i + u_j N_j \Rightarrow u^{(e)} = [N][u]^T$ be a linear approximation solution over the nodal element e , $y_i \leq y \leq y_j$ where $u^{(e)} = [u_i, u_j]$ and $N = [N_i, N_j]$ also, u_i and u_j are the velocity component at the i^{th} and j^{th} nodes of the typical element (e) $y_i \leq y \leq y_j$. Also, N_i and N_j are called basis or (shape) functions and can be defined as: $N_i = \frac{y_j - y}{y_j - y_i}$ and $N_j = \frac{y - y_i}{y_j - y_i}$

Applying the above on (11) we get

$$M_2 \int_{y_i}^{y_j} \begin{bmatrix} N_i' N_i' & N_i' N_j' \\ N_i' N_j' & N_j' N_j' \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_i \\ u_j \end{bmatrix} dy + \int_{y_i}^{y_j} \begin{bmatrix} N_i N_i & N_i N_j \\ N_i N_j & N_j N_j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_i \\ \dot{u}_j \end{bmatrix} dy + M_1 \int_{y_i}^{y_j} \begin{bmatrix} N_i N_i & N_i N_j \\ N_i N_j & N_j N_j \end{bmatrix} dy - P \int_{y_i}^{y_j} \begin{bmatrix} N_i \\ N_j \end{bmatrix} dy = 0 \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) is simplified to get:

$$\frac{M_2}{l} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_i \\ u_j \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_i \\ \dot{u}_j \end{bmatrix} + \frac{M_1 l}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_i \\ u_j \end{bmatrix} - \frac{P}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Where $l = y_j - y_i = h$ and prime and dot signifies differentiation with respect to y and t respectively. Now we assemble the equations (13) for the two consecutive elements $y_{i-1} \leq y \leq y_i$ then the following is obtained:

$$\frac{M_2}{l^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_{i-1} \\ u_i \\ u_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 4 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_{i-1} \\ \dot{u}_i \\ \dot{u}_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} + \frac{M_1}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_{i-1} \\ u_i \\ u_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} - \frac{P}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Now consider the two-row corresponding to the node I to zero with $i = h$, from equation (16) the difference scheme reads:

$$\frac{M_2}{h^2} (-u_{i-1} + 2u_i - u_{i+1}) + \frac{1}{6} (-u_{i-1} + 4u_i + u_{i+1}) + \frac{M_1}{6} (u_{i-1} + 4u_i - u_{i+1}) = P \quad (17)$$

Using the trapezoidal rule on (15) the following system of equations in Crank-Nicolson method is obtained as:

$$A_1 u_{i-1}^{n+1} + A_2 u_i^{n+1} + A_3 u_{i+1}^{n+1} = A_4 u_{i-1}^n + A_5 u_i^n + A_6 u_{i+1}^n + P^* \quad (18)$$

Similarly applying the same method to solve equation (6) we get

$$B_1 \theta_{i-1}^{n+1} + B_2 \theta_i^{n+1} + B_3 \theta_{i+1}^{n+1} = B_4 \theta_{i-1}^n + B_5 \theta_i^n + B_6 \theta_{i+1}^n + Q \quad (19)$$

$$C_1\varphi_{i-1}^{n+1} + C_2\varphi_i^{n+1} + C_3\varphi_{i-1}^n = C_4\varphi_{i-1}^n + C_5\varphi_i^n + C_6\varphi_{i+1}^n + R^* \tag{20}$$

Where:

$$A_1 = 2 - 6M_2r + rM_1h^2, A_2 = 8 + 12M_2r + rM_1h^2, A_3 = 2 - 6M_2r + rM_1h^2$$

$$A_4 = 2 + 6M_2r - rM_1h^2, A_5 = 8 - 12M_2r - rM_1h^2, A_6 = 2 + 6M_2r + rM_1h^2,$$

$$B_1 = Pr - 3r, B_2 = 4Pr + 6r, B_3 = Pr - 3r, B_4 = Pr + 3r, B_5 = 4Pr - 6r, B_6 = Pr + 3r$$

$$C_1 = Sc - 3r, C_2 = 4Sc + 6r, C_3 = Sc - 3r, C_4 = Sc + 3r, C_5 = 4Sc - 6r, C_6 = Sc + 3r$$

$$Q = 6rPr \left[Ec \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right]^2 - D_f \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} - R\theta_i^n \right] P^* = 12rh^2(G_r\theta_i^n + G_c\varphi_i^n) R^* - 6rh^2Sc \left[K_r\varphi_i^n - S_r \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} \right]$$

4. Results and Discussion

This study explored the effects of thermo-diffusion and thermal radiative MHD flow over an exponentially vertical plate. To analyze the physical behavior of the flow, graphical results for velocity, temperature, and concentration profiles were generated. Additionally, tables showing the values of skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number were compiled to provide further insight into heat and mass transfer characteristics. To investigate the behavior of these flow parameters, various key dimensionless quantities were selected with the following default values: brick-man ($B_r = 0.1$), Jeffery fluid parameter ($\beta = 0.1$), grashop number ($G_r = 2$), Solutal Grashof number ($G_c = 2$), hall current parameter ($m = 0.1$), radiation parameter ($R = 0.1$), Magnetic field parameter ($M = 1$), ($S_r = 1$), Prandlt number ($P_r = 0.1$) and perturb parameter ($\epsilon = 0.5$).

To verify the accuracy and validity of the numerical solutions obtained using the finite element method, a comparative analysis was conducted. **Figure 2** and **Table 1** present a direct comparison between the results of the present study and those reported by Abdullahi et al. (2024). The comparison clearly demonstrates that the current results show good agreement with the previous study, confirming the reliability and correctness of the numerical procedure used in this investigation.

Figure 2: Comparison between the results of (Abdullahi et al., 2024) and current results when $R = 0, S_r = 1, G_r = 0, m = 0.1, G_c = 0,$ and $\epsilon = 0$

Table 1: displays the comparison between the results of (Abdullahi et al., 2024) and present results on τ , N_u and S_h varying magnetic parameter (M)

Previous Results				Present Results		
M	τ	N_u	S_h	τ	N_u	S_h
1	0.132526	0.027587	0.328362	0.132533	0.027596	0.328362
2	0.127188	0.027109	0.328362	0.127196	0.027200	0.328362
3	0.122104	0.026656	0.328362	0.122112	0.026667	0.328362

Figure 3: Impact of β on u

Figure 4: Impact of B_r on u

Figure 3 illustrates how the velocity profile responds to changes in the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β). The graph shows that as β increases, the fluid velocity decreases. This deceleration occurs because a higher Jeffrey fluid parameter signifies an increase in the fluid's relaxation time or viscoelastic nature, which leads to greater resistance within the convection system. As a result, the fluid flow slows down. **Figure 4** highlights the effect of increasing the Brinkman number (B_r) on the velocity profile. The graph demonstrates that a higher Brinkman number leads to an increase in velocity. This is because the Brinkman number represents the conversion of kinetic energy into internal energy (enthalpy). The rise in B_r indicates that more energy is being retained in the system, which in turn enhances fluid motion and accelerates the flow.

Figure 5: Impact of G_c on u

Figure 6: Impact of G_r on u

Figure 7: Impact of m on u

Figure 8: Impact of R on u

Figure 9: Impact of M on u

Figure 10: Impact of ϵ on u

Figure 5 shows the effect of the Solutal Grashof number (G_c) on the velocity profile. As illustrated, the fluid velocity increases with a rise in G_c this occurs because a higher solutal Grashof number generates stronger buoyancy (upthrust) forces due to concentration gradients. These forces reduce the fluid's resistance to flow (i.e., effective viscosity), resulting in enhanced fluid motion. Figure 6 presents the influence of the thermal Grashof number (G_r) on the velocity profile. The graph reveals that increasing G_r leads to a significant acceleration of fluid velocity. This is because a higher G_r corresponds to a greater ratio of buoyancy forces to viscous forces, promoting faster fluid movement due to temperature-induced density variations. Figure 7 depicts the effect of the hall-current parameter (m) on the velocity profile. The results show that velocity decreases as m increases. This is due to the fact that Hall current reduces the thermal conductivity of the fluid and weakens the Lorentz force, which is responsible for opposing the fluid motion in a magnetic field. Consequently, the fluid flow slows down. Figure 8 illustrates the impact of the radiation parameter (R) on the velocity profile. The graph indicates that the velocity increases significantly with rising R . This is because stronger thermal radiation enhances the thermal energy within the fluid, thickening the thermal boundary layer and promoting faster fluid motion. Figure 9 shows the effect of the magnetic field parameter (M) on the velocity profile. As M increases, the velocity decreases. This is due to the action of the Lorentz force, which resists the fluid flow when exposed to a magnetic field, thereby reducing the fluid's velocity. Figure 10 demonstrates that the velocity profile slightly increases with higher values of the perturbation parameter (ϵ). The perturbation parameter introduces oscillations in the system, contributing modestly to an increase in fluid velocity.

Figure 11: Impact of β on θ

Figure 12: Impact of R on θ

Figure 13: Impact of P_r on θ

Figure 14: Impact of M on θ

Figure 15: Impact of K_r on ϕ

Figure 16: Impact of S_r on ϕ

Figure 11 illustrates the effect of the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β) on the temperature profile. The graph shows that as β increases, the fluid temperature also increases. This happens because a higher Jeffrey parameter implies greater fluid relaxation time, which enhances the fluid's capacity to retain heat, resulting in a higher temperature within the convection system. **Figure 12** highlights the significant temperature rise associated with increasing the radiation parameter (R). As R grows, the mean absorption coefficient decreases, allowing more heat flux to accumulate in the fluid. This leads to a stronger thermal energy build-up, enhancing the heat transfer rate and raising the temperature profile. **Figure 13** shows that the temperature profile decreases with an increase in the Prandtl number (P_r). A higher P_r corresponds to lower thermal conductivity, which reduces the ability of the fluid to transfer heat. This results in a thinner thermal boundary layer and consequently, a lower temperature distribution. **Figure 14** demonstrates the influence of the magnetic field parameter (M) on the temperature profile. As M increases, the fluid temperature decreases. This is due to the Lorentz force, which suppresses the fluid motion, reducing the convective heat transfer and leading to a drop in temperature. **Figure 15** presents the effect of the chemical reaction parameter (K_r) on the concentration profile (ϕ). The graph shows that increasing K_r leads to a reduction in concentration. This happens because a stronger chemical reaction intensifies molecular collisions, which thins the concentration boundary layer and reduces overall concentration in the system. **Figure 16** illustrates the impact of the Soret number (S_r) on the concentration profile (ϕ) the concentration increases with rising S_r . The Soret effect introduces thermal diffusion, generating temperature gradients that enhance mass transfer and cause an increase in concentration within the fluid system.

Table 2: Impact of R on τ , N_u and S_h

R	τ	N_u	S_h
0.1	0.436695	0.553878	0.328315
0.2	0.623653	1.067031	0.328272
0.3	0.968451	2.222524	0.328177

Table 3: Impact of G_c on τ , N_u and S_h

G_c	τ	N_u	S_h
0.1	0.436695	0.553878	0.328315
0.2	0.721391	0.934899	0.3282786
0.3	1.184211	1.732099	0.328201

Table 4: Impact of B_r on τ , N_u and S_h

B_r	τ	N_u	S_h
0.1	0.436695	0.553878	0.328315
0.2	1.173115	3.414040	0.328041
1.3	3.611258	25.017321	0.325848

Table 5: Impact of β on τ , N_u and S_h

β	τ	N_u	S_h
0.1	0.436695	0.553878	0.328315
0.2	0.414176	0.528231	0.328041
0.3	0.392499	0.504890	0.328317

Tables 2 to 5 were generated using **MATLAB** to illustrate the impact of various parameters on **skin friction** (τ), Nusselt number (N_u), and Sherwood number (S_h). These parameters include the radiation parameter (R), solutal Grashof number (G_c), Brinkman number (B_r), and Jeffrey fluid parameter (β).

Tables 2 and 3 show that increasing both the radiation parameter (R) and solutal Grashof number (G_c) leads to a significant enhancement in skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number. This indicates stronger momentum, heat, and mass transfer as these parameters grow. **Table 4** demonstrates that higher Brinkman numbers (B_r) causes a substantial increase in skin friction and Nusselt number, while the Sherwood number decreases. This suggests that although fluid flow and heat transfer are intensified, mass transfer is somewhat suppressed. **Table 5** reveals that an increase in the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β) results in a slight reduction in skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number. This is due to the viscoelastic effects of Jeffrey fluid, which tend to dampen both fluid motion and transfer rates.

5. CONCLUSION

This study explored the This study investigates the effects of thermo-diffusion and thermal radiative MHD flow over an exponentially vertical plate. The major findings from the analysis are summarized below:

- i. Fluid velocity increases with higher Brinkman number (B_r), perturbation parameter (ϵ), solutal Grashof number (G_c), thermal Grashof number (G_T), and radiation parameter (R). Conversely, velocity decreases as the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β), hall-current parameter (m), and magnetic field parameter (M) increase.
- ii. The temperature profile rises with increasing radiation parameter (R). However, it decreases when the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β), Prandtl number (P_r), and magnetic field parameter (M) are intensified.
- iii. The concentration profile reduces as the chemical reaction parameter (K_r) increases. In contrast, concentration increases with higher Soret number (S_r).
- iv. There is a notable improvement in skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number with the intensification of the radiation parameter (R) and solutal Grashof number (G_c).
- v. A slight reduction in skin friction, Nusselt number, and Sherwood number is observed when the Jeffrey fluid parameter (β) increases

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Appendix

Nomenclature and Creeks Symbols

B_r	Brick-man Number	C_w	Wall Dimensional Concentration
K	Thermal Conductivity	C_∞	Ambient Concentration
P_r	Prandlt Number	C^*	Dimensional Concentration
T^*	Temperature of the fluid Close the Plate	g	Accelerature due to Gravity
t^*	Dimensional time	C_∞^*	Ambient Fluid Concentration
K	Porosity Parameter	S_c	Schmidt Number